

**TRANSMISSION AND PRESERVATION OF *AFRABIC*
MANUSCRIPTS OF NORTH CENTRAL NIGERIA FOR
KNOWLEDGE DEMOCRATIZATION, SCHOLARSHIP AND
RESEARCH ECONOMY¹**

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Abstract

Nigeria is home to a vast and largely untapped repository of Arabic and *Ajami* manuscripts. These manuscripts—preserved in private libraries, mosques, emirate archives, and family collections—document centuries of Islamic scholarship, local governance, medicine, astronomy, and socio-cultural life. Despite their historical and academic value, many of the manuscripts are at risk of extinction due to poor preservation, lack of trained personnel, and minimal institutional coordination. This has made this intellectual heritage gradually losing its significance in the world of intellectual development. This study thus attempts to showcase the veritable potentials as well as the scholastic eclecticism embedded in the *Afrabic* Manuscripts as local heritage assets and material culture with particular reference to selected North Central Nigeria. It situates the significance of these manuscripts in the mills of knowledge production, democratization, scholarship and knowledge economy. It proposes the necessity of preserving and transmitting the manuscripts by integrating these material culture of Nigerian origin into the Nigeria’s cultural and academic framework. The study thus proposes the need for establishing a sustainable, interdisciplinary academic programme that produces skilled professionals in Arabic Manuscriptology, supports the documentation, preservation, and promotion of Nigeria’s Islamic manuscript heritage in collaboration with the National Council for Manuscripts

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and Monuments. It equally proposes postgraduate-level training in *Afrabic* manuscriptology, codicology, and heritage preservation, where there is opportunity of developing a bilingual digital archive of Nigeria's Islamic manuscripts; foster collaboration between academia and cultural heritage institutions as well as capacity building platforms for heritage-based community engagement and education.

Keywords: *Afrabic* manuscriptology, North Central Nigeria, Knowledge Democratization, Scholarship and Research Economy

Introduction

Afro-Arabic herein referred to as *Afrabic* manuscripts are found to be veritable items of African Indigenous heritage scattered all over African continent. Troves of these manuscripts are indispensable source material to the expanded knowledge of an all-inclusive African culture. There has been remarkable effort in continuum at introducing the Arabic literary heritage of Africa to the academic cosmos, and indeed the *Arabophile* productions, which provide an insight into an intellectual bequest. While many of these manuscripts, which have been discovered, are on the verge of total extinction, a considerable number of them have been rendered illegible by insects, climatic conditions, poor storage facilities and rot. It has been estimated that more than 80% of manuscripts in Northern Nigeria are privately owned. (Hamman & Mohammed, 2010).

Besides, some of these works particularly written by the 19th and 20th century scholars could be found in some Nigerian Universities and research centers, other items though not yet discovered but mention has been made of them or inferred to them in the extant manuscripts, it is believed that they are incredibly negligible against the reality of what is in private hands. This constitutes a problem of neglecting not only important but also significant aspect of the Afro-Arabic heritage. It is interesting to note that some Nigerian Universities and research centers have taken some interest in the Arabic Manuscripts for research and scholarship, yet there is much to be done in this area.

Afrabic and *Afrabia*, are two different words carefully coined from the word Africa and Arabic; Africa and Arabia respectively as a concept has been muted based on the idea that 'French had once examined their special relationship with

Africa and later came up with the concept of Eurafrika as a basis of special cooperation' as noted by Mazrui (See: Mazrui, 1992: 52ff). Drawing from this concept especially for the purpose of this lecture, I have decided to employ same concept of what I describe as *Afrabic* considering the fact that most of the ideas therein fall within the purview of the relationship between Africa and Arabic, which is the area of this study in particular. (Sirajudeen, 2024).

This study first identifies the extant *Afrabic* manuscripts with particular reference to the selected North Central Nigeria that are still lying in private hands. It equally describes the manuscripts and showcases not only its contents but also the intellectual significance of these manuscripts. These could purposively be used for knowledge democratization, scholarship and research. The conscious effort to preserve these manuscripts guides and catalogues via e-documentation and dissemination to academic institutions, research centers among others is for further research in the area. This significantly enables for a proposed establishing of a Center of Afro-Arabic Indigenous Science and Knowledge Systems (Afro-Arabic Manuscriptology for the postgraduate studies).

Researchers can significantly explore the uncharted terrains or aspects of indigenous science in Afro- Arabic writing traditions and identify the materials thereof with a view to complementing the existing manuscripts with more materials (manuscripts) particularly in this relatively *new* area (indigenous Science and knowledge systems). They can thus showcase the contributions of the scholars on the concepts of universality of indigenous science and its application for further laboratory research (as the case may be).

Today, in the quest for rediscovery of tradition, the search for the manuscripts, which contain these writings, has been of immense significance to the knowledge of intellectual, social and anthropological life of the African subcontinent. Most of these studies made currently on the Arabic literary traditions of Africa particularly on the ancient manuscripts have left world of early Islamic Science and Metaphysics in which Muslims lived and thought. This has equally brought into lime-light information concerning the early Afro-Arabic civilization, some of which may not be found in the usual books. It has also presented an outline of what was *known* and generally accepted, but indicating the points at which scholarly debate could continue.

The research area is North Central Nigeria, which include the concerned states within the region. States such as Niger, Nasarawa, some parts of Kwara, and some parts of Plateau are much relevant here. It is instructive to mention here that places like Kwara and Niger states have much documented Afro-Arabic Manuscripts, emphasis will be on the Nasarawa and some parts of Plateau in this context, which have not been considerably accessed in terms of this material cultural heritage.

In this sampling and site selection, which include states, emirates, libraries, families, mosques, archives, it is apposite to mention here that having access and permissions procedures, were done with the direct contact to the heirs on personal levels. The permission procedures include pre-information and requests made to the heirs especially who are ready to share via scanning and or photocopying of the available manuscripts while some others are not allowed to access their own. This category of heirs did this ostensibly preserving the family heritage. It is important to mention here too that most of the manuscripts obtained therefrom are private – owned ones.

Efforts to get similar *Afrabic* manuscripts from the emirates, libraries, mosques and or archives proved abortive. Only private families were ready to share the manuscripts. The reason is not far from the awareness personally created to these sets of heirs which made them at least released some of the materials for the purpose. The issue of description standards (codicological and cataloguing schema), digitisation workflow (hardware, resolution targets, file formats, metadata standards, repository architecture), and basic ethics (custodial rights, sensitivities around esoteric and healing materials, informed consent, restrictions) are left for other research outputs and do not form part of this present work. At present, “North Central Nigeria” is described broadly (Niger, Nasarawa, parts of Kwara and Plateau), the actual field sites covered were within Nasarawa, Plateau and Niger states. The visitation to these places was in October 2025 where a total of about 37 manuscripts identified and stored in a retrieval device for further digitization and cataloguing to be deposited in the University e-Library.

***Afrabic* Manuscripts of North Central Nigeria: Descriptive and Content Analysis**

While the National Archives house considerable number of the *Afrabic* manuscripts, more of this material culture are lying in private hands as well as private holdings of *Ulama*, Imams and religious establishments; legacy holdings of manuscripts in the custody of heirs. These *Afrabic* manuscripts are numerous and varied in forms and contents. There are considerable number of them across West and some parts of East and South Africa. A significant portion of them are documents written in Arabic and *Ajami*. They deal with both religious and extra-religious subjects. The development of the manuscripts traditions dates back to the early days of Islam in West Africa, in the 11th century. In addition to these Arabic and *Ajami* manuscripts, there have been others written in indigenous scripts. They are found in the trove of the manuscripts got from the field.

It is essentially pertinent to declare here from the onset that, this work does not include that of Ilorin Emirates, which significantly constitute that of Kwara Central as a considerable effort have been made by Moshood Mahmood Jimba, (2019) in this regard. This study first sets to search for transmitting and preserving trove of Afro-Arabic Manuscripts found in the private hands with particular reference to the North Central Nigeria. This is primarily for the purpose of use in further research into the African Indigenous Science and knowledge systems ever found in these material culture.

The manuscripts are undoubtedly veritable treasures that deal with various subjects. They include official correspondence, private letters, business records and discussions on labor and agriculture, slave trade and freedom, gold and currency, and divination and geomancy. Some deal with Arabic language and grammar, African languages, dialectology, logic, astrology, law, politics, pharmacology and medicine, alchemy, philosophy, ethics, sociology, history, diplomacy between European and African rulers in the pre-colonial era, political economy, chemistry, geography, government legislations, and astronomy as well as other aspects of humanities and scientific endeavors. They contain the secrets of plants and a wealth of esoteric knowledge. Each of the folio describes the content whether in Arabic or *Ajami* (African languages written in Arabic script).

Descriptions of the Afrabic Manuscripts

More than Muslim religion, the *Afrabic* Manuscripts constitute yet the reality more complex as *Afrabic* material culture *albeit* in addition to the religious aspects, the manuscripts are rich in scientific contents and deal with themes that are still of utmost relevance in contemporary period (Sirajudeen, *et al*, 2023). Various Arabic manuscripts of today's Nigerian Muslim scholars from Kanem-Borno Empire and Sokoto caliphate contain discourses on various subjects such as Law, Theology, Qur'anic and Hadith Sciences, Philosophy, Language, Linguistics, Literature, Administration, Politics, Sociology, History, Education, Astronomy and Mathematics (Umar, M.A. (2007). Umar, M.A. (2007) cited British Library Board thus:

...Manuscripts from Africa cover a wide chronological span and diverse subjects, including literature, poems, narratives, historical accounts, chronicles, and Biblical, religious, medical, cartographic, geographic and other texts. They include Qur'ans in Arabic from Morocco and Egypt, and from West Africa copied by Hausa scribes, some of which are lavishly illustrated or illuminated...

Following Galadanci, (2007) classification pattern of the Arabic manuscripts on Northern Nigeria, the Arabic Manuscripts of north central Nigeria could be categorized in to the following: First were the Arabic Manuscripts into this region by other Muslim scholars such as Qur'an, Books of Hadith. These include works written by unknown visiting scholars. Secondly, there are the works of notable scholars of the present-day Niger and Nasarawa States. To this class belongs Shaykh Waziri Bida and others. The third category are some unknown scholars. The fourth class consists of works by authors.

It is interesting to point out here that a considerable number of these *Afrabic* Manuscripts obtained in the recent search in the North Central Nigeria are not with the names of their author nor that of the title of the subjects. Efforts have been made to identify some of them as far as one could and categorize them according to the contents. This is one of the major challenges and travails of the obtained manuscripts in this region. However, it is instructive to note that despite

these perceived deficiencies, yet researchers could benefit immensely from the manuscripts. Excerpts therefrom serve as bases for knowledge democratization and scholarships. (See some folios below:

Other significant aspects of the manuscripts in addition to their contents testify to the art of calligraphy. The broad range of scripts includes Oriental, Maghribi, Saharan (the most common in Timbuktu) Sudani from Nigeria and the Tuareg Suqi script, reflecting the reach of the city's influence. The manuscripts also exemplify the art of illumination and protective leather binding (Ahmadu Hampate Bah, 1973).

Contents Analysis of the Afrabic Manuscripts of the region

The literary works of the Nigerian Arabic authorship demonstrate their erudition in the aspects of mathematics, medicine, and animal science. This in addition to the religious teachings and learning. There are some other works on these subjects, which are contributions on the concepts of universality of scientific knowledge and others on the spirit of unity, patriotism and nationalism. Their writings on *‘ilm al hisab*, for example, reveal their erudition in the mathematical sciences as the whole range of methodology in their computation using *‘ilm al hisab* and *al awfaq* is found to be purely mathematical. Also, their extensive use of a particular branch of *hisab* called *‘ilm al jabr* (algebra) is evident in their commentaries of issues relating to meteorology including their scientific explanations of a number of phenomena of both physical and spiritual significance (Ibrahim, *et al*, n.d).

For instance, in what Hunwick (ed. 1995) reluctantly categorize as secular in the Arabic writings of the Nigerian authorship, there are some of the literary works of the *‘Ulama’* which do not belong to the traditional religious sciences of Islam but have been incorporated therein as earlier on explained. Such disciplines concern mostly physical, mathematical sciences, logic, and history. Others include medicine and its related branches. On account of its classical of Arabic scholarship, the Arabic writings in this part of the world have enjoyed renowned for some of these subjects mentioned above and has equally set it apart from other Saharan communities.

However, unlike the various subjects that are found among the earlier Arabic scholars in the area of mathematical sciences such as the ones that relates to horology (*ilm al mawaqit*), astronomy (*al Falak*), astrology (*al Tanjim*), chronogram (*ilm al hisab*) and meteorology, north central Nigerian Arabic manuscripts especially the ones at hand do not have such. Available manuscripts indicate subjects such as Literature, Language, Jurisprudence, Siirah – History, talisman, and other related topics as contained in the folios. Perhaps the fact that most of the heirs of either the authors and or the custodians of the manuscripts are afraid of loosing their heritage by hoarding these material culture as it is seen and considered as exclusive property of the family must have accounted for the loss or altogether unavailability of many of the manuscripts being accessible for the purpose. This is unconsciously killing the revival of the African material cultural heritage of this category.

Among the contents of the manuscripts, we found what could be referred to Healing Therapy. In what is not dissimilar to other Arabic manuscripts of African origin regardless of the region, the scholars who are encyclopedic in their religious as well as quasi-religious activities have produced trove of the material culture that were used for healing to both psychological and physiological ailments (Sirajudeen, *et al.*: 2023). A good number of the Arabic manuscripts of the north central Nigerian origin contains information on healing therapy. These manuscripts are of both prophetic and secular formulas which are written in both Arabic and Ajami scripts.

Sirah of the Prophet of Islam is another prominent subject found in these manuscripts collected electronically for preservation and documentation for further use. While there are number of texts, old and new written by scholars on the life and times of the Prophet of Islam, north central Nigerian Muslim scholars still tried to demonstrate their erudition especially in the artistic form by writing in verse the biography of the Prophet Muhammad. It is pertinent to note here that one of the voluminous works found in this region was on this subject carefully written in *Rajaz* rhyme. The folio contains a detailed biography of the prophet. (see a sample here)

Arabic Grammar and Arabic Syntax also formed part of the retrieved *African* manuscripts of the north central Nigeria. It is interesting to know that the folios

containing the teaching of Arabic syntax to the local students in verse demonstrates the erudition of the authors most of which are not known as their names are conspicuously missing on the front page of the writings. Yet, one cannot but acknowledge the efforts made in this area of pedagogy especially as a kind of indigenouse approach to teaching foreign language – Arabic.

Fig: 1

Title: No Title

Author: الطاهر الملقب بغيم في مدينة لافيا

Copyist: Unknown

Call Number: 001

Date: scanned October, 2025

Number of folios: 49

Ink color: black

Contents: Arabic Morphology

Kundi (Material Culture) as well as healing therapy and related themes are part of the contents of the Afrabic manuscripts of the North Central Nigeria. In a related development, a therapy in one form or another exists in every nomadic society, yet among the Muslim scholars of this region like their counterparts in other climes, certain elements of medical knowledge were equally found. Appointed but designated prayer formulas where a mathematical or conventional talisman is considered most effective were prescribed. In some cases, secret scripts, numbers, or signs and the divine text are recited and written and drunk. The form of recitation by invocation is noticeable in the poetry where the poet mentioned nay! invoke the blessing of God via the divinity of the Qur'an against the attack of any ailment – physiological and psychological. The use of letters, secret of numbers and divine texts is another form of this science.

Fig: 2

Title: تحفة الولدان

Author: الحاج محمد بن محمد بن الحاج عبد الله البرناوي

Copyist: Unknown

Call Number: 002

Date: scanned October, 2025

Number of folios: 16

Ink color: black

Contents: supplication prayer formula

Travelogue is another subject found amongst the manuscripts of the region. Travelogue is a literary genre found mostly in the works of *Afrabic* literati from the medieval periods till the contemporary period. Describing the geographies, histories as well as peopling and adventures has become literature on its own. Such descriptions and the numerous information contained therein are but subjects of intellectual contribution that lends credence to knowledge democratization, research and scholarships. The contributions of *Afrabic* literati to the growth and development of this genre is significant as could be found in the available manuscripts.

Fig: 3**Title:** وصف البلدان**Author:** Unknown**Copyist:** Unknown**Call Number:** 003**Date:** scanned.

October, 2025

Number of folios: 11**Ink color:** black**Contents:** Travelogue

Jurisprudence is mostly found subject in these manuscripts. Reproduction of texts on Islamic *Fiqh* are found in the works written by the scholars who sometimes might not include their names at the end of the writings. In the areas of literature, there are considerable number of folios on *qasaa'id* (Odes) of various topics; panegyrics, elegy, *wa'z wa Irshad*, biographies, autobiographies, as well as some other religious and *quasi*-religious subjects.

It is important to note that in describing the broader Nigerian manuscript universe, the broader West African universe, and or the specific North Central sample, and considering the fact that this study is a preliminary presentation, the three “Fig” entries are presented here as brief catalogue-like summaries without reproductions, a consistent metadata standard, and without analysis that demonstrates how these examples were selected and what they represent statistically or thematically in the wider collection.

Afrabic Manuscripts of North Central Nigeria in the Mills of Knowledge Democratization

There is no doubt that the Afro-Arabic manuscripts are more significant than what is imagined in constituting a *new* knowledge, scholarship and research enterprise. Since the beginning of the first half of the last century, there have been concerted efforts in the study and research on the Arabic manuscripts of Muslim West

African authorship. Studies and researches are however, mostly conducted on the much collected and systematically documented Arabic manuscripts of the scholars. Most of the Arabic manuscripts, which deal with various subjects such as indigenous science and its usage, are so much held in awe that could not be easily accessed especially by *outsiders*. Hunwick, (1964: 43) has rightly observed that 'we have not yet full access to many of these books and papers, though a number have generously permitted us to examine their collections and photograph any works of interest.' This has constituted a huge vacuum in the African Indigenous Science and Knowledge Systems.

Considering the significance of these Afro-Arabic manuscripts to the expanded knowledge of African indigenous science and knowledge systems, there is need to explore and have full access to many more of these material culture especially in the North Central Nigeria. This will enhance further dissemination of knowledge, which are apparently *old* but also useful in this contemporary period. Hence, while other Arabic manuscripts have been accessed and documented fragmentarily as we could have them, this category in the North Central Nigeria is equally very rare to come by. There is no doubt that there is need to single out these manuscripts, get it digitized and documented for further research considering the invaluable significant of these manuscripts to the intellectual development of the region.

Further research has been conducted on the efficacy of the knowledge embedded therein and its relevance particularly to the contemporary intellectual development as a contribution of Arab-Islamic writings of the West African Arabic scholars to global and contemporary multicultural dimensions. It has thus opened a new vista in this aspect of the Islamicate African as it equally opened up a relatively unexplored – not necessarily unfamiliar – aspect of the pre-colonial traditions of the West African Arabic literary traditions. There is no doubt that the *West African Arabic Manuscripts in the processes of knowledge production and transmission with particular attention to the knowledge and epistemologies are buried therein as a new medium for an authentic African voice in socio-cultural expression and scholarship.*

These *Afrabic* manuscripts today have become more useful in sustainable, interdisciplinary academic programme for skilled professionals in Arabic

Manuscriptology. More than religious orientation of the contents of the manuscripts, *Afrabic* manuscripts contributed to indigenous science and knowledge system as alternative therapy. Elsewhere, I have tried to work on illustrated interdisciplinary research mostly based on the contents of some *Afrabic* manuscripts of the Nigerian authorship. Here, the idea of interdisciplinary academic programme for skilled professionals in Arabic Manuscriptology has been demonstrated and has equally elicited a new vista in contemporary knowledge economy. Knowledge democratisation in this context, however indicates open access digitisation, community access, educational curricula, public humanities programming and data sovereignty. It relates to existing debates in manuscript studies, heritage studies, and digital humanities in Africa.

Documentation, preservation, and promotion of Nigeria's Islamic manuscript heritage are other aspects of the *Afrabic* manuscripts of the region. While this present project focuses on documentation, preservation and dissemination of these material culture, it tends to complement the existing related materials from some other regions. The significance of these tools is immense in various areas of human endeavors. This could be found in the contents of the available manuscripts as described earlier. In doing this, researchers could access these documents for further research, scholarships and knowledge economy. It makes research into the African past history, anthropology, sociology, religion and economy easier and more accessible. Hence, the need for it now.

The documentation and preservation of the *Afrabic* manuscripts here provides immense opportunity for postgraduate-level training in *Afrabic* manuscriptology, codicology, and heritage preservation. This is a veritable avenue not only in reviving the near extinct African intellectual heritage but also presenting same for contemporary knowledge democratization and scholarships. It is important to note here that while training the trainers especially in the area of Arabic manuscripts is common in some other climes, same is yet to gain popularity in Nigerian higher educational institutions (HEIs).

The reason being that there is little or no such interest in the intellectual understanding of the contents of the manuscripts and its significant contributions to the scholastic development of the regions. Therefore, inclusion of the African Manuscriptology into the curricula of the Arabic Studies in Nigerian Higher

Institutions. The process of democratizing knowledge through the Afrabic manuscripts also calls for collaboration between academia and cultural heritage institutions. This will enhance the desired capacity building platforms for heritage-based community engagement and education.

Preservation and Transmission of the *Afrabic* Manuscripts: Triumphs and Travails

Islamicate Africa has pre-occupied the centerpiece of research in contemporary era. It has been argued in some quarters that Africans are limited by a kind of epistemological slavery, where we use conflicting Western systems of knowledge production in producing African Knowledge. We rely on Western methodologies for knowledge production, Western schooling system for how we engage with and use the knowledge, and even Western systems for how we store and preserve the knowledge. While the discussion of epistemological slavery and reliance on Western methodologies as mentioned here raises a legitimate decolonial question, that engage Africanist decolonial method debates and also a nuanced acknowledgement that digitisation standards and metadata schemas are not inherently “Western” in a civilisational sense, but tools whose governance and ownership can be localised. There is no doubt that currently

In the bid to ostensibly safeguarding most of these Arabic manuscripts from total extinction and particularly as family intellectual property, there has been continued hoarding and secrecy of these material culture especially by the heirs. This has constituted a serious challenge to accessing this significant heritage. It has equally disallowed for the democratization of knowledge embedded therein for universal diffusion and transmission of valuable heritage. Consequently, this is pushing the manuscripts together with its significant values into total oblivion. The significance of these invaluable treasures of African heritage especially in the indigenous science and knowledge system, creative economy and further intellectual scholarships are found in the preparation for global knowledge democratization.

Today, these treasures of learning and craftsmanship are exposed to all kinds of dangers: termites can eat the paper, fire can burn it, water can erase the writings and damage the paper, acidity can destroy the paper, and wind can scatter the

pages...many enemies lie in wait. There is still insufficient knowledge of the actual number of the Arabic manuscripts, their authors, contents and locations. This has constituted a kind of monumental challenges to the significant treasure.

Conclusion

Since the beginning of the first half of the last century, there have been concerted efforts in the study and research on the Arabic manuscripts of Nigerian authorship. Studies and researches are however, mostly conducted on the much collected and systematically documented Arabic manuscripts of the scholars. Besides, it is also observed that only a handful of the Arabic manuscripts of much Nigerian Muslim authorship are collected and not yet systematically documented in a digitized form (Sirajudeen, 2008). Hunwick (1964) has rightly observed that 'we have not yet full access to many of these books and papers, though a number have generously permitted us to examine their collections and photograph any works of interest.

We are not unaware of the presence of Arabic manuscripts of indigenous *Ulama* particularly in north central Nigeria many of which are still resting in private hands. Hence, while other Arabic manuscripts have been accessed and documented fragmentarily as we could have them, this category is very rare to come by. There is no doubt that there is need to single out these manuscripts for further research considering the invaluable significant of these manuscripts to the intellectual development of the region. There are numbers of Arabic writings to the credit of these scholars in manuscripts on these subjects. However, there are other items though not yet discovered but mention has been made of them or inferred to them in the extant manuscripts. Centre of Arabic Documentation in the Institute of African Studies, University of Ibadan houses many of these works particularly written by the 19th and 20th C. scholars.

This study suggests transmission and preservation of the collected Arabic Manuscripts of the North Central Nigeria in the e-Library of Museums, Archives, Universities and public libraries. This is done by digitizing the collected manuscripts. It has espoused the process of transmitting, preserving and digitizing considerable Arabic Manuscripts sampled with particular reference to the north central Nigeria thereby making it available for researchers - postgraduate students

and staff - for dissemination of knowledge, scholarships as well as further research economy. Publication of the catalogues, edited manuscripts, periodic seminars, workshops and exhibitions will enhance further research by students and staff in manuscripts scholarships.

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